

THE LANDSCAPE OF BEHAVIORAL FINANCE: A BIBLIOMETRIC ANALYSIS

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Abstract

The study seeks to delve into the development of the behavioral finance domain, aiming to discern trends and patterns in knowledge development. Additionally, it aims to comprehend the current trend within the domain. A bibliometric analysis within the realm of behavioral finance was conducted on a dataset comprising 931 documents. The analysis was carried out using a scientific search strategy applied to the Web of Science database for the timeframe spanning 1995 to 2023. The study employed Biblioshiny, a web-based application integrated into the Bibliometrix package developed in R-language (Aria and Cuccurullo, 2017a). The software's automated workflow facilitated the identification of prominent journals, authors, countries, articles, and themes. Furthermore, the analysis encompassed citation, co-citation, and social network analysis. The findings indicate a notable development in the thematic focus of behavioral finance, demonstrating a shift over time from market-centered research to a greater emphasis on studies rooted in human psychology. In addition to unveiling the conceptual structure, this investigation sheds light on the intellectual and social dynamics within the domain. The study offers valuable insights, identifying specific areas that warrant further exploration. Since extensive conceptual and empirical efforts have been conducted on a global scale within the domain of behavioral finance. This study significantly contributes to the behavioral finance literature by synthesizing the current literature in the field, highlighting noteworthy sources, authors, and documents, while simultaneously pinpointing opportunities for future research efforts.

Keywords: Behavioral Finance, Bibliometric Analysis, Behavior, R software, Biblioshiny

1. Introduction

Traditional finance has long been the basis of financial theory and practice establishing a structured framework for comprehending the way financial markets behave and the manner in which decisions are made by economic agents. Rooted in principles of rationality, efficiency and market equilibrium, traditional finance theories have laid the groundwork for much of modern financial analysis. The theory assumes that investors behave rationally while making various kinds of decisions (Muhammad and Maheran, 2009). It consists of various concepts and theories, such as the expected utility theory (Bernoulli, 1896), Markowitz portfolio principles (Markowitz, 1952), the capital asset pricing model (Treynor, 1961) etc., to explain the efficiency of the market that contains all the available information while taking financial decisions (Kumar and Goyal, 2015; Zahera and Bansal, 2018). The traditional theories such as Efficient Market Hypothesis (EMH) and Modern Portfolio Theory (MPT) have shaped the landscape of investment strategies and risk management. EMH posits that asset prices fully reflect all available information, implying that it is

impossible to consistently achieve above-average returns through market analysis or information asymmetry. MPT, on the other hand, emphasizes the importance of diversification in constructing portfolios to optimize risk-return trade-offs.

However, the real-world complexities of human behaviour began to challenge these assumptions and inability of these theories to explain the market anomalies such as the formation of market bubbles and market crashes (Sharma and Kumar, 2020; Zahera and Bansal, 2018) led to the view that market participants are not always rational and often exhibit cognitive biases and emotional influences in their decision-making process. Several studies like Ahmad et al., 2017; Feldman and Lepori, 2016; Shrotryia and Kalra, 2021a; Tversky and Kahneman, 1979 supports the fact of investor irrationality while making investment decisions along with the stock market anomalies such as high volatility and stock market ups and downs. This change in the view became the base for inception of a new field, behavioral finance. Behavioral finance combines cognitive psychology and thoughts of leaders in economics, finance and behavioral psychology to explore the driving forces behind the financial decisions that people make (Pujara and Joshi, 2020). It helps to explain the difference between expectations of efficient, rational investor behavior and actual behavior (Veni and Kandregula, 2020).

Behavioral finance as a discipline attempts to explain and increase understanding regarding how cognitive errors or the mental mistakes and emotions of investors influence the decision making. It focusses upon how investors interpret and act on information to make informed investment decisions. Tversky and Kahneman (1974) were the first to identify psychological biases in investment decision making under uncertainty. The various cognitive biases identified by researchers among individuals include anchoring, representativeness and availability (Tversky and Kahneman, 1974); loss aversion, mental accounting, regret aversion (Tversky and Kahneman, 1979), disposition effect (Shefrin and Statman, 1985), overconfidence (Odean, 1998), and home bias (French and Poterba, 1991; Tesar and Werner, 1995), among others (Baker *et al.*, 2019; Shrotryia and Kalra, 2021b). With further developments in behavioral finance Shefrin (2002) categorized these biases into heuristic-driven biases and frame-dependent biases while Montier (2002) classified biases into three categories namely self-deception, heuristic simplification and social-interaction. Being the pioneer of Behavioral Finance Amos Tversky and Daniel Kahneman explored psychological factors that affect financial choices, leading to the development of prospect theory, which explains how individuals deviate from rational decision-making due to cognitive biases. (Tversky and Kahneman, 1979). Behavioral finance incorporates insights from psychology, sociology, and other social sciences to explain market anomalies, bubbles, and crashes that cannot be fully explained by traditional financial theories. It explains the effects of mental factors on financial decision making and how people think about money and investments (Chandrakala and Kamal, 2024) This evolution underscores the importance of recognizing the human element in financial decision-making, enriching our understanding of markets and providing valuable insights for investors and policymakers alike.

With the growing interest and researches in behavioral finance, it is absolutely necessary to analyze the evolution and the current status of Behavioral Finance (Paule-Vianez *et al.*, 2020). To understand the expansion in the field, the current study embarks on a bibliometric analysis, delving into extensive body of research that explores behavioral finance.

Bibliometric analysis studies use mathematical and statistical techniques to analyze patterns in literature that is already published (Singh and Dhir, 2019). It enables us to unpack the evolutionary nuances of a specific field, while shedding light on the emerging areas in that field (Donthu *et al.*, 2021a). It is an analytical technique used for quantitative analysis of scholarly works (Donthu *et al.*, 2021b; Kraus *et al.*, 2022; Lim *et al.*, 2022; Mukherjee *et al.*, 2022; Paul *et al.*, 2021). In the past few years, works on bibliometric analysis in the domain of finance have been published in areas such as financial literacy, accounting research, green finance, supply chain finance, information and communication technology and financial education (Ingale and Paluri, 2022). Thus, with the goal to analyze the progress in the behavioral finance, this study employs bibliometric analysis tools to evaluate significant developments by addressing following research questions.

1.1 Research Questions

1. Which are the most influential journals and authors in the field of behavioral finance?
2. How has the concept of behavioral finance evolved?
3. What is the current state of behavioral finance?

The above questions translate to following research objectives attained through the study

1. To elicit the trends or patterns in knowledge development in the area of behavioral finance.
2. To investigate the current trends in behavioral finance.

The further article is organized as follows. The next section provides details regarding research methodology used, followed by data analysis and findings. Subsequent two sections conclude the study with conclusion and future research directions.

2. Research Methodology

Analysis of the study began with identification of database, followed by data collection based on search strategy (Figure 1)

Figure 1: Flowchart for document selection for Bibliometric analysis

The required data was retrieved following the identification and selection of a suitable database. After choosing the database, pertinent data was extracted using relevant keywords.

2.1 Selection of Database

The data was retrieved using Web of Science(WOS) database due to its compatibility with R software that is used for analysis. Also, WOS is widely recognized for its comprehensive database and its inclusion of documents from top-tier journals make it an apt choice for bibliometric analysis.

2.2 Preparing Data for Analysis

To match the requirements of software, data was downloaded from Web of Science in plaintext format after shortlisting the documents based on search criteria applied on 29th November 2023.

Data was extracted by conducting a topic search from Web of Science core collection using keywords. Topic search provides coverage of title, abstract, author keywords and keywords plus. Keywords used for search included words from both US and UK English to get a comprehensive view.

2.2.1 Search Strategy

Keywords: "Behavioral Finance" OR "Behavioural Finance" (Topic)

Document Types: Article, Early Access, Review Article, Proceeding Paper, Book chapters

Languages: English

Timespan: 1995-2023

Indexes: SCI-EXPANDED, SSCI, AHCI

2.2.2 Selection of time span: With objective to detect trends and perspectives in the field of behavioral finance data included all publications from 1995 to 2023. The year 1995 was selected as the year of inception for the study as it was the base year for data on Behavioral Finance in Web of Science.

2.2.3 Selection of Document types: Retracted publications and Data papers were excluded thus covering articles, early access, review article, proceeding paper and book chapters for further analysis.

2.2.4 Selection of Language: Shortlisted documents were further refined through language filter – “English” thus extracting final dataset of 931 documents.

Meta data of these documents were downloaded in plain text format to meet the requirements of analysis software Biblioshiny (R software).

2.3 Selection of Bibliometric tool

This study applies the bibliometric technique for analysis using Bibliometrix R-package, a tool created in R language by Aria and Cuccurullo, 2017b. This software allows extensive bibliometric research ranging from data analysis to its visualization in an easy and user-friendly way allowing even the non-coders to work efficiently. Majority of bibliometric analysis are complex due to difficult access resulting from commercial licenses or requirement of training for users. This difference in user interface makes Biblioshiny, a web-based application in Bibliometrix package apt choice for researchers.

3. Data Analysis and findings

Data analysis was structured into descriptive analysis for describing the data and scientific mapping for data visualization (Figure 2). Descriptive analysis examines the bibliometric data in terms of primary features of the data set such as sources, authors and documents. It includes the analysis of data set, sources, authors, keywords, trend topics along with a three-field plot and country-wise contribution. Scientific mapping entails substantial science mapping using visualization techniques which include network analysis, thematic maps, etc. to explain the conceptual, intellectual and social structure of the data.

Figure 2: Data Analysis

3.1 Descriptive Analysis

3.1.1 Data Set: Table1 provides a bird’s eye view of the bibliometric data frame of 931 documents shortlisted through search from Web of Science. These documents were published in 184 sources with average citation score of 25.83 and an annual growth rate of 17.62 percent. Out of these 931 documents, only 18% documents are single authored showing a domination of co-authored documents. International co-authorship stands at 26.53% showing an inclination towards collaboration between different geographical location beyond domestic country resulting in varied knowledge and expertise.

Table 1: Summary of Data Set

S.No.	Description	Results
1	Timespan	1995:2023
2	Sources (Journals, Books, etc)	184.00
3	Documents	931.00
4	Annual Growth Rate %	17.62
5	Document Average Age	6.91
6	Average citations per doc	25.83
7	Keywords Plus (ID)	1486.00
8	Author's Keywords (DE)	2359.00
9	Authors	1900.00
10	Authors of single-authored docs	143.00
11	Single-authored docs	169.00
12	Co-Authors per Doc	2.50

3.1.2 Three field plots: Three field plot (Figure 3) provides relation among three fields using Sankey Plots, where size of the portion is proportional to the value of the node (Riehmman *et al.*, 2005). The height of each box indicates the frequency of connections with other boxes (Abhishek and Srivastava, 2021). The authors are on the left side of the Sankey Plot, the keywords are mentioned in the middle row, and the sources selected for analysis have been kept on right side. Each of the ten items depicted prominent keywords like behavioral finance, behavioural finance, investor sentiment, asset pricing and market efficiency along with their sources and prolific authors. All the ten influential journals encompassed the topic “behavioral finance”. “Disposition effect”, “Overconfidence”, “Financial markets” and “Prospect theory” emerged as important sub-topics addressed by these influential authors and journals.

Figure 3: Three-field plot

3.1.3 Sources: Scientific productivity in the research domain during the period 1995-2023 showed an upward trend (Figure 4). It exhibited a surge in volume post 2008 owing to an inclination towards the researches on behavioral finance to understand the reasons for stock market anomalies against the backdrop of major downfall in stock market which began in 2007 and peaked in 2008 resulting in stock market crash around the globe.

Figure 4: Annual Scientific Production

While the scientific productivity in the field has increased, the average citation per year showed a fluctuating trend with being at peak during 1995 to 1990 whereas the researches published during recent years showed low average citations due to the time dependency (Figure 5). Majority of the documents in behavioral finance were older than 6.91 years (Table 1) depicting that the topic has not yet entered into maturity phase though the number of publications on this topic has increased continuously.

Figure 5: Average Citation per year

As explained by Low and Siegel, 2020 the growth of research domain evolves through the following phases: (1) Precursor, (2) exponential growth, (3) consolidation of body of knowledge and (4) decrease in the number of articles (Ingale and Paluri, 2022). On being compared with the aforementioned stages, the concept of behavioral finance was placed in the growth stage with a constant rise in the number of publications.

A detailed analysis of the sources revealed most cited journals, most relevant sources in the field, most impactful sources along with production of these sources over time. The top 10 most cited journals being indicative of the quality of journal in the field are presented in the Figure 6.

Figure 6: Most cited journals

Journal of finance has the maximum citations followed by Journal of Financial Economics whereas the Journal of Behavioral Finance became the most relevant source for behavioral finance studies (Figure 7) followed by Journal of Banking & Finance and Journal of Behavioral and Experimental Finance.

Figure 7: Top 10 Most Relevant Sources

Apart from being the second most relevant source for behavioral finance researches, Journal of Banking & Finance is the most impactful journal in the field (Figure 8).

Figure 8: Top 10 impactful sources

If we pay attention to the production of sources over the time frame of 1995 to 2023 as presented in figure 9, Journal of Economic Behavior & Organization was a major producer for behavioral finance studies in the initial phase.

Figure 9: Sources Production Over Time

Over time new journals began publishing the researches of behavioral finance. With the increase in inclination towards behavioral finance studies post 2008 as indicative through the increased scientific production (Figure 3), studies were more aligned towards a dedicated journal for the field, Journal of Behavioral Finance. This journal was established in the year 2000 with the name Journal of Psychology & Financial Markets but was renamed to Journal of Behavioral Finance in 2003. As the production of researches in the field of behavioral finance got pace, this journal also gained the momentum leaving other journals publishing in the field way behind maintaining its top position since 2012.

3.1.4 Authors: Yang CP, Muga L, Hirshleifer D, Santamaria R and Kliger D were the most relevant authors in the field of behavioral finance (Figure 10) making great contributions to the field while Hirshleifer D emerged as the most impactful author in behavioral finance having the highest h-index (Figure 11).

Figure 10: Most relevant authors

David Hirshleifer (Hirshleifer D) being an American economist associated with reputed institutions like University of California and National Bureau of Economic Research had immensely contributed to the field by producing research papers like “Investor psychology and Security under and Overreactions”(Daniel *et al.*, 1998), “Investor Psychology and Asset Pricing”(Hirshleifer D, 2001) and “ Herd Behaviour and Cascading in Capital Markets: A review and synthesis”(Hirshleifer and Hong Teoh, 2003). Due to lack of clear information available about Teoh Sh., one of the most impactful authors, is excluded from the analysis.

Figure 11: Author Impact

3.1.5 Country-wise contribution: Figure 12 shows the contribution of different countries in the field. Developed countries has contributed the most to the literature in this area with USA having the majority of the publication in the field followed by China, UK and France. Figure 13 shows that USA had shown a steep rise in the production since 1995 along with being the highest cited country amongst the top 10 countries (Figure 14) with other countries being way behind it.

Figure 12: Country's Scientific Production

USA is way ahead of other countries as significant contributors of the field such as Richard Thaler, Daniel Kahneman and Robert Shiller were based in USA. USA has one of the most dynamic and largest stock market with a rich history of data availability.

Figure 13: Country production over time

Having being the home for world’s leading universities and research institutions and with a supportive government and regulatory body towards researches, USA has maintained its spot in the field of research contributing prominently to behavioral finance. With a developing positive approach and support towards researches, other countries have started moving up in the production of researches in the field of behavioral finance as evident from the Figure 13.

Figure 16: Trend Topics

3.1.8 Prominent articles in the field of behavioral finance

Table 2: Prominent Articles

1	Fama, 1998	Market efficiency, long-term returns, and behavioral finance	Journal of Financial Economics	1788
2	Baker and Wurgler, 2007	Investor sentiment in stock market	Journal of Economic Perspectives	1552
3	Shiller, 2003	From Efficient Markets Theory to Behavioral Finance	Journal of Economic Perspectives	629
4	Abreu and Brunnermeier, 2003	Bubbles and Crashes	Econometrica	469
5	Huang et al., 2014	Tone Management	The Accounting Review	320
6	Hirshleifer et al., 2004	Do investors overvalue firms with bloated balance sheets?	Journal of Accounting & Economics	314
7	Kaplanski and Levy, 2010	Sentiment and stock prices: The case of aviation disasters	Journal of Financial Economics	311
8	Daniel et al., 2002	Investor Psychology in capital markets: evidence and policy implications	Journal of Monetary Economics	291
9	Glaser and Weber, 2007	Overconfidence and trading volume	The Geneva Risk and Insurance Review	278

10	Oechssler et al., 2009	Cognitive abilities and behavioral biases	Journal of Economic Behavior & Organization	268
11	Malmendier and Shanthikumar, 2007	Are small investors naive about incentives?	Journal of Financial Economics	246
12	Campbell, 2000	Asset Pricing at the Millennium	The Journal of Finance	238
13	Boswijk et al., 2007	Behavioral heterogeneity in stock prices	Journal of Economic Dynamics & Control	231
14	Kearney and Liu, 2014	Textual sentiment in finance: A survey of methods and models	International Review of Financial Analysis	230
15	Jiang et al., 2005	Information Uncertainty and Expected Returns	Review of Accounting Studies	227
16	Bursztyn et al., 2014	Understanding Mechanism Underlying Peer Effects: Evidence from a Field Experiment on Financial Decisions	Econometrica	218
17	Masini and Menichetti, 2012	The impact of behavioural factors in the renewable energy investment decision making process: Conceptual framework and empirical findings	Energy Policy	203
18	Ofek et al., 2004	Limited arbitrage and short sales restrictions: evidence from options markets	Journal of Financial Economics	184
19	Ichev and Marinč, 2018	Stock Prices and Geographic Proximity of Information: Evidence from the Ebola Outbreak	International Review of Financial Analysis	183
20	Mian and Sankaraguruswamy, 2012	Investor Sentiment and Stock Market Response to Earning News	The Accounting Review	176

Table 2 presents the most influential articles as per their total citations. In the field of behavioral finance, the study by Fama (1998) is the most influential research article published in Journal of Financial Economics, with 1788 citations. This is followed by Baker and Wurgler (2007) in the Journal of Economic Perspectives with 1552 citations and Shiller (2003) in the Journal of Economic Perspectives with 629 citations. Fama (1998) in his paper “Market efficiency, long-term returns, and behavioral finance” (highly cited article) examines long-term anomalies, concluding they often result from methodological issues rather than true market inefficiencies, supporting the resilience of the market efficiency hypothesis while the second most cited paper by Baker and Wurgler (2007) developed a top-down approach to understand behavioral finance and its empirical effects on the stock market focussing on investor sentiment. They provide empirical evidence that sentiment influences individual, firm and the market as a whole, thus, highlighting the importance of understanding how sentiment affects cost of capital and the allocation of corporate investment between safer and more speculative firms.

Theme in the right top corner “risk, return and market” showing high degree of centrality and density reflects the motor themes in the area which implies them being the most discussed topic. The themes “performance, behavior and prospect-theory” in the left bottom corner are the emerging or declining themes in the area as they show low density and low centrality.

Figure 18: Thematic Map

3.2.1(iii) Thematic Evolution: The examination of thematic evolution in the field involves capturing the overarching trajectory of the field's development over time. This process entails dividing the entire timeframe into distinct time slices. The guidance for the evolution of the research area is derived from assessing the centrality and density of both keywords and fields within each temporal segment (Chen *et al.*, 2019; Della Corte *et al.*, 2019; Ingale and Paluri, 2022). This study employed thematic evolution analysis with a 150-word count encompassing keywords plus field, along with a minimum cluster frequency of five. The examination spanned three time slices, demarcated by cut points in 2004 and 2014 (Figure 19-21).

The study delineates that investor psychology, decision-making, and equilibrium constitute niche themes, while returns, earnings, efficiency, market, and consumption collectively form the motor themes. Intermediate positions between niche and emerging or declining themes are occupied by stock returns, contrarian investment, and extended functional fixation, whereas risk, prices, and habit formation fall between emerging and basic themes. Basic themes encompass information, performance, and winners within the field from 1995 to 2004 (Figure 19).

Figure 19: Time slice 1- Thematic evolution during 1995-2004

Notably, stock returns experience growth in both density and centrality, shifting towards motor themes from 2005 to 2014, while risk assumes an increasingly prominent role as a fundamental research theme (Figure 20). Simultaneously, performance attains heightened certainty, establishing itself as the core basic theme during this period, with model and behavior as coexisting basic themes.

Figure 20: Time slice 2- Thematic evolution during 2005-2014

The emergence of uncertainty as a niche theme and the market's transition from motor themes to the declining or emerging category during 2015-2023 are noteworthy. Over this period, returns evolve from motor themes, and risk shifts from an intermediate position among emerging and basic themes to become the core basic theme (Figure 21).

Figure 21: Time slice 3- Thematic evolution during 2015-2023

During this timeframe, expectations and the stock market reside within the emerging field, whereas performance, behavior, and prospect theory emerge as motor themes. Employing a three-field plot facilitates capturing the emergence of broad and core themes. An in-depth examination of interlinkages among themes across three temporal spans—1995-2004, 2005-2014, and 2015-2023—underscores the thematic evolution. In the initial period, six themes (information, investor psychology, returns, market, stock returns, and risk) merge with the market in the second period, predominantly aligning with the theme of risk in 2015-2023. The prominence of risk in the second period emanates from the influx of information, returns, market, stock returns, and risk from the first period, converging significantly with risk and market in the third period. Uncertainty from the first period predominantly converges with decision-making in the second period, ultimately merging with performance. A theme from the second period, namely performance, intertwines with information, investor psychology, and returns from the first period, blending with performance, news, and model in the third period. Investor psychology and market combine with equilibrium in the second period, culminating in risk, performance, and model in the third period.

3.2.2 Intellectual Structure: The intellectual structure assesses the influence of different authors on the scientific community through an examination of author and country collaborations. This analysis unveils the degree of cooperation among research groups, the scholarly community, and their affiliations with various institutes (Cobo *et al.*, 2011; Mendes *et al.*, 2017).

Figure 22 reveals the co-citation analysis. Co-citation analysis focuses on examining the connection between articles that cite and those that are cited. The frequency of co-citation reflects how often a specific set of articles is referenced together, suggesting a shared thematic connection among them (Ingale and Paluri, 2022). Using papers as the unit of analysis, incorporating 50 nodes, and applying the Louvain clustering algorithm, the diagram reveals three clusters of authors denoted by distinct colors. In Cluster 1, depicted in red, Kahneman D emerges as the most influential author, boasting the highest betweenness centrality measure. Odean T, Shefrin H, and Tversky A also make noteworthy contributions to the field of behavioral

finance within this cluster. The second cluster, in blue, features authors like Baker M and Delong JB, exhibiting betweenness centrality measures of 29.86 and 34.76, respectively. The third cluster highlights contributors such as Daniel K, Fama EF, Barberis N, and Jegadeesh, who have made substantial contributions to the field of behavioral finance.

Figure 22: Co-citation analysis

3.2.3 Social Structure: Social Network Analysis (SNA) was undertaken to unveil the interrelationships within the research domain. As illustrated in the fig. 23, the scholarly inquiry is predominantly led by the USA from a regional standpoint. Researchers from the USA demonstrate robust collaboration with scholars in China, the United Kingdom, France, Australia, Canada, Israel, and Italy. The second significant contributor in the field is China, collaborating closely with Australia, the United Kingdom, Singapore, Canada, and Pakistan. Additionally, a distinct group of contributors is spearheaded by the United Kingdom, partnering with France, Australia, the Netherlands, Germany, and Ireland.

Figure 23: Social network analysis

4. Conclusion

The study examines the evolution of behavioral finance domain from 1995 to 2023, employing bibliometric analysis to highlight patterns in authorship, citations, sources, and countries, as well as identifying high-impact authors and collaboration trends. Utilizing the Web of Science database and Biblioshiny, a web-based application of the Bibliometrix package in R software, the study reveals that the Journal of Behavioral Finance is the most significant journal, followed by the Journal of Banking & Finance. Developed countries, particularly the USA, dominate contributions and citations, while the study suggests a need for increased research from developing economies like India. The assessment delves into the conceptual, intellectual, and social structure of the behavioral finance domain, showcasing its development and shift from risk-and-return-centric studies to those focusing on gender differences, behavioral biases, and decision-making. The paper provides a roadmap for academics and practitioners, offering insights into existing knowledge and uncovering further research opportunities. In essence, this research demonstrates the field's progress, encourages the construction of a knowledge base, and identifies unexplored facets of behavioral finance, aiming to inspire additional studies by various stakeholders.

5. Future Research Direction

For the purpose of this study, the data has been retrieved from Web of Science database. Other database such as PubMed, Scopus, Dimensions or Lens can also be used. Second, R software has been used to analyze the data, while the researchers in future may opt for different software such as Vosviewer or a combination of different software. Third, the study has used Bibliometric analysis while more detailed analysis can be done using literature review, meta-analysis, etc. The study reveals that majority of studies are produced in nations like USA and UK thus highlighting the need and scope for more studies in developing nations like India. Conducting more research in behavioral finance in countries like India can lead to better understanding of the unique factors influencing financial decisions such as diverse culture, financial inclusion policies, technology adoption, etc.

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